

Leveraging blockchain to tackle food fraud: Innovations and obstacles

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ABSTRACT

Blockchain is a virtual, distributed ledger that operates across multiple peer-to-peer computing devices without the need for a centralized authority. It utilizes unique software systems to manage transaction data file (block), facilitating the transmission, processing, storing, and display of data. As a solution to combat food fraud and enhance food safety, blockchain technology is gaining traction in the global food supply chain. It provides an immutable ledger system and transparent record-keeping, which offers unmatched traceability and accountability, enabling stakeholders to track food products from farm to fork. Despite its potential, the adoption of blockchain in the food industry faces challenges such as scalability, interoperability, and data accuracy, which need to be overcome to fully utilize its capabilities. This study aims to provide a comprehensive overview of how blockchain technology address food fraud and improves food safety. By employing a review methodology, we analyze existing literature and case studies to examine blockchain's role in enhancing transparency, traceability, and sustainability in the food supply chain. This study identifies research gaps and discusses theoretical implications, practical applications, and potential future directions for blockchain technology within the context of food safety. Our findings highlight the transformative potential of blockchain to revolutionize the food industry by providing unparalleled traceability and accountability. We also emphasize the importance of collaborative efforts among stakeholders and the integration of innovative approaches such as decentralized data adjustment and the inclusion of genomic information on blockchain platforms. Theoretically, further research is needed to explore the synergy blockchain and emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things and Artificial Intelligence. Practically, our study underscores the critical need for blockchain adoption to safeguard the integrity of the food supply chain and protect consumer health. Through collective action and technological innovation, stakeholders can ensure that every food product is traceable, safe, and trustworthy, thereby enhancing the sustainability and resilience of the food industry.

1. Introduction

Food fraud significantly undermines the integrity of the global food and agri-food marketing system [1]. This malpractice not only poses health risks, potentially causing diseases or even death, but also leads to financial losses for consumers. They end up paying for a quality of food they do not receive, and their health may be compromised by fraudulent food products. Additionally, incidents of food fraud erode consumer trust in the food industry and the government agencies that regulate it [2], further damaging public health and trust. Examples of food fraud include the case where melamine was deliberately added to Chinese infant milk products to illegally boost the nitrogen content, falsely indicating a higher protein content level. This adulteration resulted in severe health issues like kidneys stones and other kidney related

illnesses, affecting approximately 300,000 infants and children in China and leading to six fatalities [3]. Another notable case is the “horse meat scandal”, which emerged in 2013 in British and Irish markets. In this incident, horse meat was discovered in products that were labeled as containing 100 % beef [4]. These incidents not only heightened consumer awareness but also led to improvements in legislation and global food safety standards. However, more enhancements are necessary to ensure food authenticity, which is crucial for all consumers, especially those with specific dietary needs or religious dietary restrictions [5].

Globalization and technological competition have significantly increased the complexity of the food supply chain, involving numerous actors and factors. Traditional systems struggle to provide effective and dependable traceability solutions, which are increasingly demanded for greater accountability and transparency within the food supply chain

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[6]. In response, industry 4.0 has introduced advanced technologies such as blockchain, which are now being embraced worldwide by theorists and business practitioners alike to enhance the traceability and transparency of the food supply chain (FSC) [10]. Blockchain technology is seen as potentially transformative for the food industry, offering benefits, such as flexibility and transparency. These features allow for a reliable and secure tracking system that monitors food products from origin to end consumer, ensuring comprehensive traceability [6].

The Food Safety Net Services (FSNS) defines food fraud as an intentional act of mislabeling, substituting, or modifying a food product at any point from production to consumption [7]. The prevalence of food fraud is alarmingly high, for instance, between 2016 and 2019, the number of suspected cases in European Union (EU) countries rose by 85 percent [8]. The Food and Drug Administration estimates that food fraud impacts about one percent of the global food industry, costing up to \$40 billion annually [9]. Such widespread fraud not only results in significant financial losses but also poses serious risks to consumer health and erodes trust in the food industry [8].

One approach to mitigating food fraud is through networks like the EU Agri-Food Fraud Network (EU FFN) and the Food Authenticity Network, which promote collaboration and information sharing. Additionally, technology, especially digital traceability systems such as blockchain, plays a crucial role. Blockchain technology enables the tracing of food products throughout the supply chain and helps identify the sources of food fraud [11]. For instance, the European Institute for Innovation and Technology (EIT) Food supports innovators who utilize this technology to increase transparency and traceability. A notable example includes EIT Food Risings SwissDeCode, which has developed DNA tests to quickly verify the authenticity and safety of food products, ensuring that fraudulent foods are intercepted before entering the supply chain [11]. Despite the significant challenges posed by food fraud globally, blockchain offers a viable technical and economic solution. It provides unmatched transparency and traceability from the producer to the consumer. This decentralized and immutable ledger system allows for the verification of food products authenticity and the detection of counterfeit trades [12].

Blockchain technology is being adopted across various industries to solve transaction issues and enhance security. For example, major companies like IBM are implementing blockchain throughout the production and supply chain to enable real-time monitoring of food conditions, reducing the risk of food-related illness [10]. However, blockchain technology is not without its drawbacks, including scalability issues, high energy consumption, and integration complexity. Innovation solutions like energy-efficient consensus mechanisms such as Proof of Stake (PoS), layer two technologies for improved transaction throughput, and workload distribution strategies like sharding have been developed to address these challenges [13]. Community involvement is essential for advancing blockchain technology, which includes enabling different blockchain systems to interact, integrating with the Internet of Things (IoT), and developing privacy-enhancing methods. These initiatives aim to make blockchain technology more efficient, flexible, and impactful, with a strong potential to reduce food fraud significantly [14].

In summary, blockchain is increasingly recognized within the food industry as a preventive measure against food fraud, which includes mislabeling, ingredients substitution, and false claims about food quality [6]. The technology facilitates a transparent and immutable record of food products' journey from farm to table, making it easier to pinpoint where fraud occurs within the supply chain. This capability makes blockchain a promising tool in the ongoing fight against food fraud [14]. The technologies are integrated into the food system through a unique digital tag assigned to each product, which is then tracked using smart contracts and Internet of Things (IoT) sensors throughout all stages of the supply chain. This creates a transparent and easily traceable path, thereby reducing the likelihood of undiscovered fraudulent activities. For instance, if a product's "Made in" label is tampered with to falsify its

origin, the blockchain will record this discrepancy, showing a mismatch between the actual production location and the label [16]. A study by Ref. [19] showed that combining blockchain with IoT can potentially prevent \$31 billion in food fraud over five years, having significant economic impacts. Additionally, the complex and global nature of modern food supply chains amplified the risk of fraud. However, the end-to-end visibility provided by Blockchain acts as a deterrent, preventing adulteration and misrepresentation of food products, which helps protect consumer health and enhances trust in the food sector.

Despite the growing interest in using blockchain technology to enhance food safety and traceability, there is a significant gap concerning its practical implementation and real-world impact within the food industry. While numerous studies have explored the theoretical aspects of blockchain, comprehensive research focusing on its actual application and effectiveness in real-world food supply chain scenarios remains limited. The research is motivated by the urgent need to address food safety issues and enhance transparency throughout the food supply chain. Our goal is to explore blockchain's potential and contribute to the development of innovative solutions that can protect consumer health and enhance confidence in the food industry.

This paper proposes a future research agenda to further explore this field, emphasizing areas such as regulatory frameworks, technological advancements, and industry collaborations. These areas are critical for understanding how the adoption of blockchain can be accelerated, thereby improving traceability and integrity within the food chain. Moreover, this paper explores the complexity of blockchain technology and its applications in combating food fraud. We will review innovative case studies where blockchain implementation has been successful, analyze the barriers to its adoption, and discuss its potential future impact on the food industry. Through this study, we aim to provide a thorough understanding of how blockchain technology can transform food safety measures and restore trust in food supply.

The novelty of this research lies in its focused examination of blockchain technology as a solution to combat food fraud and enhance traceability within the food industry. This study acknowledges the complex challenges food fraud presents globally, including significant financial losses and serious risks to consumer health and trust. While food fraud has been addressed through regulatory networks and increased awareness, this research underscores the transformative potential of blockchain technology in ensuring food authenticity from production to consumption.

This paper advances the discourse by highlighting blockchain's application beyond theoretical exploration, addressing the practical implementation challenges and real-world effectiveness. The research is driven by the urgent need for enhanced food safety measures and greater transparency in supply chains. Through a comprehensive analysis of blockchain's ability to provide transparent, immutable records and its integration with other technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), the study proposes innovative solutions to improve food traceability and reduce fraud risks. Moreover, this research sets a future agenda to explore regulatory frameworks, technological advancements, and industry collaborations that could accelerate blockchain adoption in food supply chains. It also aims to fill the significant research gap by providing detailed case studies and analyzing barriers to blockchain adoption, positioning the technology as a critical tool for restoring trust and ensuring the integrity of the global food supply. Our study offers more specific benefits compared to the recent study of Vern et al. [14] by focusing directly on the critical issue of food fraud and safety, which are pressing concerns in the global food supply chain. By targeting these areas, our research provides actionable insights that can immediately impact consumer health and safety, helping to safeguard the integrity of the food system. Additionally, our emphasis on the synergy between blockchain and emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) enhances the practical relevance of our findings for future innovation in food safety.

2. Blockchain technology

The use of blockchain technology has seen a significant increase in recent times. Initially introduced to the public in 2008 as a fundamental component of Bitcoin, a cryptocurrency, blockchain provides a way to handle transactions without needing a central authority. Essentially, blockchain functions as a decentralized system for recording transactions. Each “block” in a blockchain securely contains transaction data and links to other blocks to form an unchangeable chain. This setup ensures that as new transactions are made, they are added to new blocks, creating a secure, tamper-proof record of all transactions. In simpler terms, blockchain is a method of data storage designed to keep information unalterable and safe from unauthorized alterations or cyberattacks [20]. The typical process of a transaction in a blockchain is outlined below.

The integration of various digital technologies, including RFID tags, NFC, Automatic Identification and Data Capture (AIDC) systems, mechanical and biological sensors, time-temperature indicators, smartphones, and digital signatures [22], facilitates the generation of real-time information across multiple stages of the food supply chain. These stages encompass environmental monitoring, production, processing, packaging, storage, transportation, and distribution of food products. This real-time data can be securely logged into blockchain systems using smart contracts after validation through a consensus process among all participants. This approach ensures that the data recorded on the blockchain is immutable and accepted by all involved parties [23].

Blockchain itself is a virtual, distributed ledger that operates across multiple peer-to-peer computing devices without the need for a central authority. It utilizes unique software systems to manage transaction data file (block), allowing for the transmission, processing, storing, and display of data in formats that are easily readable by humans [23]. The application of blockchain technology in the food sector is still in its early stages but is rapidly evolving, as evidenced by an increasing array of studies, trials, and projects exploring its use [17]. Early research highlights the necessity of blockchain in the food sector for two main reasons: it provides a more efficient tracing system that can quickly pinpoint the source of contamination during food safety crises, and it helps build consumer confidence in food safety [24]. As the global agri-food supply chains become more complex and intertwined, addressing food fraud has become a critical issue for consumers and industry stakeholders alike [25]. Blockchain technology offers a promising solution by enhancing traceability, transparency, accountability, and sustainability within these supply chains.

Blockchain significantly enhances transparency, traceability, and accountability within the food supply chain, thereby minimizing food fraud. By establishing a detailed, immutable record of all transactions from production to retail, blockchain ensures that each transaction is recorded in an unchangeable ledger. This allows all stakeholders in the supply chain to add data, making it possible for consumers to track the journey and origin of their food products easily. This visibility is crucial for verifying the authenticity and quality of food items, and it prevents data manipulation after entry [25]. Smart contracts on the blockchain automate enforcement of safety and quality standards by embedding these conditions within the code [114]. This feature ensures that products only advance in the supply chain after meeting specified requirements, enhancing compliance and reducing the risk of contamination. Blockchain’s real-time tracking capabilities and its secure, tamper-resistant technology further enhance accountability, allowing swift responses to any supply chain issues [115].

For consumers, blockchain technology increases trust by providing transparent access to a product’s history through simple actions such as scanning a code with a smartphone. This capability is especially valuable during recalls, enabling quick identification and removal of contaminated items, thereby enhancing food safety [42]. Blockchain also helps ensure regulatory compliance, as all stored data is easily

accessible to auditors and regulatory bodies to verify adherence to food safety standards. Additionally, it plays a critical role in combating counterfeiting, particularly in verifying the authenticity of premium and organic products, ensuring consumers receive the quality they pay for and reducing the risk of mislabeling or adulteration [43]. Overall, blockchain’s role in the food supply chain not only reduces the risk associated with food fraud but also boosts consumer confidence and safety [115].

3. Innovations of blockchain for food fraud prevention

3.1. Blockchain technology and enhanced transparency, traceability, and sustainability

Blockchain technology is significantly improving the traceability and transparency of the food supply chain, crucial for combating food fraud. The technology allows for detailed tracking of food products from their origins [10], fulfilling both regulatory requirements and increasing consumer demands for precise, authentic product information. Traditional food supervision systems face challenges such as data fragmentation, limited interoperability, and transparency issues caused by data inconsistencies [26]. Blockchain addresses these issues by integrating technologies such as RFID and cloud computing to enhance visibility across the food supply chain [10]. Recent research conducted by Ref. [25] highlights the critical roles of blockchain’s immutable ledgers and robust data security in combating food fraud [27], tackling contamination sources, and verifying food safety from production to consumption. Innovative applications include the “FarMarketplace” a blockchain-based platform designed to connect farmers directly with third-party stakeholders, protecting farmers’ rights and ensuring fair trade [28].

In 2017, [JD.com](#), a prominent Chinese e-commerce platform, collaborated with Kerchin, a beef manufacturer in Inner Mongolia, to implement a blockchain-based traceability system for turkeys. Utilizing the Hyperledger Fabric platform, this system enabled consumers to access comprehensive information about each turkey, including its origin, nutritional profile, food safety test results, and slaughtering process [29]. By the following year, [JD.com](#) extended its blockchain initiative to beef supplies sourced from Australia, announcing its intention to apply blockchain technology across its entire meat supply chain to enhance traceability and transparency [30]. This expansion aimed to address growing consumer demand for detailed food origin information and to strengthen food safety measures. In a notable development, [JD.com](#), in partnership with IBM, Walmart, and the Tsinghua University National Engineering Laboratory for E-Commerce Technologies, established a blockchain alliance to improve food safety through enhanced traceability. The alliance’s inaugural focus was on pork traceability, involving major suppliers and retailers such as Dole, Driscoll’s, Kroger, and Golden State Foods [31]. This collaboration reflects a significant industry effort to create a more transparent and secure food supply chain. Similarly, in 2018, Alibaba launched a trial on its T-Mall platform to track international food shipments, working with Australian company Blackmores and New Zealand’s Fonterra. This initiative aimed to provide consumers with verifiable information on the provenance and handling of international food products [32].

In 2019, Bumble Bee Foods, a prominent seafood company headquartered in the United States, collaborated with the German technology giant SAP to develop an advanced blockchain-based seafood traceability system. This innovative system allows consumers to scan a QR code on their seafood products to access a comprehensive array of information. Specifically, the system provides details about the origin of the seafood, including the exact catch size, the geographical location where the seafood was captured, the entire shipping history, and any relevant trade certifications. This traceability system aims to enhance transparency, ensuring that consumers can make informed choices and verify the authenticity and sustainability of their seafood purchases

[30].

Similarly, a case study presented by Ref. [33] explored the deployment of a public blockchain-based traceability system for the egg supply chain, developed by Bytable Inc. in collaboration with Farmers' Hen House. This system represents a significant innovation in food traceability by enabling consumers to scan a QR code on egg cartons to access detailed information about the eggs' origins. The information provided includes the specific farmer who produced the eggs, photographs of the farm, the farming practices used, and any relevant certifications related to the egg production process. This level of transparency helps build consumer trust and supports informed purchasing decisions by offering insights into the production and handling practices associated with the eggs. By integrating blockchain technology into these supply chains, both Bumble Bee Foods and Bytable Inc. have set new standards for traceability in the food industry. These systems not only enhance consumer confidence by providing verifiable information but also contribute to greater accountability and integrity in the food supply chain. The use of blockchain technology in these initiatives demonstrates its potential to revolutionize food traceability and ensure that consumers have access to accurate and comprehensive information about the products they purchase.

Blockchain technology holds the potential to significantly alter current business practices in the food supply chain by promoting sustainability. This technology enhances the security and transmission of data within a decentralized, peer-to-peer framework while permanently recording transactions. Such features of blockchain can reduce fraud, ensure fair trade and labour practices, and help minimize waste and carbon emissions in the food supply chain [34–36]. Blockchain also supports credible organic product certifications, enabling strategies for green sourcing and the development of eco-friendly design practices in food production [37]. Additionally, the increased transparency and traceability afforded by blockchain are spurring the development of green products, contributing to the food industry's sustainable growth. Enhanced customer awareness and easy access to product information via blockchain can also pressure businesses to improve their corporate responsibility efforts [38].

In the agriculture sector, blockchain is being leveraged by small-scale farmers to address challenges in financing, planning, production, transportation, and retailing, thus enhancing social, economic, and environmental sustainability. Various blockchain-based platforms assist farmers by facilitating easier access to financial services, enabling food origin traceability, and supporting peer-to-peer transactions. For example, Dimitra, a platform built on the Ethereum blockchain for the global grains industry, helps farmers worldwide reduce dependency on middlemen by integrating Blockchain with advanced technologies such as AI, IoT, and satellites [39]. This integration aids farmers in collecting essential data, making prompts and informed decisions, enhancing crop yields, and decreasing waste and emissions. Furthermore, these platforms offer green certifications, helping farmers earn customer trust.

TE-FOOD is a public, permissioned blockchain-based food traceability system designed to enhance transparency across the entire food supply chain, from the farm to the consumer's table. Participants in the supply chain, including smallholder farmers, maintain master nodes which allow for detailed tracking of food-related information [39]. This system has been adopted by thousands of farmers globally, for example, Hungarian Angus cattle farms have implemented TE-FOOD to monitor various operational aspects such as activities on the farm, in the slaughterhouse, processing facilities, and along the logistics chain [40]. The system records and stores comprehensive information including details about feeding practices, medication usage, veterinary checks, transportation, packaging, and the energy usage and emissions at each step of the supply chain. Customers can access this detailed information by scanning QR codes on the products. The use of TH-FOOD not only helps farmers stand out from their competitors but also aids in building stronger brand recognition through increased transparency. The application of blockchain technology, demonstrated by TE-FOOD, shows

significant promise in creating a safer, more transparent, and sustainable agricultural food system. However, it is important to recognize that the widespread implementation of blockchain in the agri-food sector is currently dominated by large-scale retailers. Small farmers often face significant financial and technological hurdles that limit their ability to adopt such advanced technologies independently.

3.2. Smart contracts and decentralized data sharing

The adoption of blockchain technology in the food industry offers a system that is both tamper-proof and transparent, ensuring shared yet secure access to information. This technology is particularly effective when paired with smart contracts [41], which are part of what is commonly known as Blockchain 2.0 Smart contracts, originally introduced by the early development of blockchain [42], are now a fundamental component in enhancing blockchain applications. These contracts are digital protocols that facilitate the automatic execution of agreements based on specific pre-established conditions, effectively removing the possibility of data manipulation or censorship [43].

In the context of the food industry, smart contracts on the blockchain manage various aspects of food transactions, such as enforcing food safety standards, food quality certifications, and adherence to regulations like HACCP (Hazard Analysis Critical Control Point), Good Agricultural Practices, and Good Manufacturing Practices. These contracts activate automatically at different stages of the food supply chain [44]. If any part of the food process – from production to delivery – fails to meet the necessary standards, the smart contract will automatically halt the process and prevent any further entry of compromised data into the blockchain system [45]. This process ensures that consumers receive reliable and comprehensive information about the products they purchase, accessible by scanning a QR code on product packaging. This capability not only boosts consumer trust but also streamlines the management of food quality and safety, enhancing the integrity of the entire farm-to-fork journey [27].

[47] put forward a blockchain-centered platform has been developed that leverages smart contracts, QR technology, and the Internet of Things (IoT) to enhance the safety and traceability in India's dairy supply chain, specifically focus on products such as milk, butter, and cheese. This platform is designed to tackle issues related to food traceability and to ensure the nutritional quality of dairy products by identifying and mitigating risks of adulteration and contamination. Moreover, it seeks to enhance production efficiency. The framework has been effective in identifying and removing adulterated and contaminated items from the supply chain, thereby building trust among participants and facilitating the resolution of conflicts. The use of smart contracts further helps reduce costs in supply chain management by eliminating the need for intermediaries [27].

Another study of [48] introduces a blockchain-cloud fusion scheme that employs a Decentralized Attribute-Based Signature (DABS) to facilitate safe data sharing among departments within food businesses. This scheme creates a decentralized, trust-based environment that allows data owners to securely exchange information and supports social co-governance of food safety. It integrates well into existing system architectures and address performance limitations commonly associated with blockchain and cloud storage. Security analysis of the scheme shows it provides complete anonymity and can effectively resist collusion attacks, even if nearly all involved attribute authorities are compromised.

These innovations in blockchain technology are proving beneficial in combating food fraud (See Table 1). Case studies, such as JD.com's blockchain-based tracing system for beef and Bumble Bee Foods's seafood traceability system, illustrate how blockchain enhances consumer trust by providing a transparent record from the food's origin to the consumer. Furthermore, smart contracts and decentralized data sharing mechanisms, exemplified by the Indian dairy industry platform and other initiatives, streamline supply chain processes, reduce costs, and

Table 1
Blockchain innovations in food fraud prevention.

Innovation	Description	Examples	Impact
Transparency and traceability	Utilizes immutable ledgers to securely track food products from their origin to the consumer.	JD.com's partnership with Kerchin for beef traceability; Bumble Bee Foods' seafood traceability system.	Enhances the ability of stakeholders to verify the history, quality, and safety of food products, thereby enhancing consumer trust.
Smart contracts and decentralized data sharing	Automates the execution of contracts based on predefined conditions, removing the need for intermediaries.	Blockchain-centered platform for the Indian dairy industry [47]; "FarMarketplace" [28].	Reduce costs, improves safety and traceability, and aids in resolving conflicts among stakeholders.

improve product safety, reinforcing blockchain's crucial role in preventing food fraud.

4. Uniqueness of blockchain compared with other industrial 4.0 technologies

Industry 4.0, emerging from the digital revolution, is characterized by four foundational types of disruptive technologies: connectivity, analytics and intelligence, human-machine interaction, and advanced engineering. Connectivity technologies, such as blockchain and the Internet of Things (IoT), enhance secure inter-device communication. Analytics and intelligence technologies, including machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI), are employed to refine data analysis and bolster decision-making capabilities. Human-machine interaction technologies like virtual reality (VR) and robotics improve interactions between humans and machines, enhancing efficiency and operational capabilities. Finally, advanced engineering technologies such as additive manufacturing (3D printing) and renewable energy innovations lead to more sustainable and flexible production methods [18,49]. Collectively, these technologies enhance productivity, and sustainability, facilitating smarter decision-making and customization across various stages of supply chain operations, from manufacturing to logistics.

The Internet of Things (IoT) plays a pivotal role in this ecosystem, primarily involving cloud computing for data management, a robust data transmission layer, and effective networking layer [50]. Key technical elements such as Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) and Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) underpin IoT systems [51]. In these systems, physical objects are equipped with sensors that have unique IP address, allowing interconnectivity between machines and other web-enabled devices [50]. This setup allows for the extensive collection, exchange, and analysis of data, which is particularly useful in areas like combating food fraud through enhanced logistics efficiency and monitoring within the food supply chain [52–54].

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) further capitalize on the information gathered, not just on the factory floor but across entire business units and supply chain networks. Machine learning (ML), a subset of AI, builds and refines knowledge models based on data through continuous learning and testing, improving with increased data use. Applications in the food supply chain include disease detection [55], quality control [56,57], and energy usage monitoring [58,59], which collectively enhance predictability and automate processes to prevent issues like food fraud [60–62].

The wider adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) faces several hurdles. First, there are security concerns, as well as challenges related to the energy consumed by AI systems. Integrating AI into complex supply

chain and logistics management networks also presents a substantial challenge due to its complexity. Moreover, there are ethical issues to consider, which further complicate its deployment. Implementing AI can be costly and resource-intensive, demanding significant technological and financial investments. Additionally, AI has inherent limitations in its learning capabilities. Unlike humans, AI systems cannot spontaneously generate creative solutions or "think outside the box." They operate strictly within the confines of the data provided and their programmed experiences, limiting their ability to adapt to new or unanticipated situations that fall outside their existing frameworks [15,63].

Virtual Reality (VR) is a technology that creates a computer-generated simulation of three-dimensional environments or images. This immersive experience allows users to interact with the virtual world in a realistic and tangible way, often through specialized equipment such as helmets with built-in screen or gloves fitted with sensors. On the other hand, Robotics is a technology focused on designing, operating, and using robots. In some scenarios, groups of robots or "swarm robots" work together to complete specific, pre-programmed tasks. Both VR and Robotics are classified as human-machine interaction technologies, emphasizing their role in enhancing the interface between humans and machines [64]. In agriculture, these technologies take on significant roles. Robotics, combined with automated control systems and AI, is integrate throughout all phases of agricultural operations, from planting to harvesting [94,95]. These advanced technologies not only automate tasks but also enhance efficiency and precision in the agricultural sector. Moreover, the food industry is actively developing state-of-the-art automation solutions and autonomous robotic systems within intelligent factory settings, pushing the boundaries of what is possible in food production and processing [65–67].

Intelligent machinery in agriculture performs a wide array of tasks such as tilling, planting, transplanting, fertilizing, spraying, feeding, watering, harvesting, and gathering crucial data on soil composition, water quality, crop conditions, and marine life. This collected data is invaluable for enhancing precision agriculture, providing essential technical support to farmers [17]. Additionally, in the realm of food production and subsequent supply chains, robotic technologies facilitate numerous processes including quality assessment, sorting, selection, packaging, transportation, and distribution, significantly automating these activities [68].

3D printing has revolutionized the creation of devices aimed at monitoring food quality, assessing package integrity, and authenticating food. This technology allows for the production of intelligent components that integrate smoothly into standard food packaging, creating what is known as Intelligent Food Packaging (IFP). These smart, 3D-printed components offer advantages over traditional manufacturing methods [69], including heightened sensitivity, self-indication, and multifunctionality, all while using biocompatible, non-toxic materials at a lower cost [69]. This innovation promotes the broader adoption of intelligent packaging, which helps reduce food waste and protects consumers from consuming unsuitable food items.

These technologies, each serving unique functions in the food supply chain, enhance operations in several ways. IoT technology connects stakeholders, enhancing collaboration and coordination throughout the food supply chain. AI mimics human cognitive processes in machines, enabling automated decision-making. Blockchain technology provides transparent and immutable records essential for managing the food supply chain, including capabilities for traceability critical or retailers, consumers, and regulators to prevent food fraud and ensure the delivery of safe, high-quality products. Table 2 provides a comparison of the main technologies in terms of their key features as well as the strengths and limitations in food management. Blockchain, in particular, is recognized for addressing transparency, traceability, and accountability challenges, essential for combating food fraud.

Table 2
Comparison of key industrial 4.0 technologies.

Technologies	Key features	Strengths in the management of FSC	Limitations	References
Blockchain (BLC)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decentralization; - Shared database structure; - Immutability of records 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure privacy, establishing trust and security;- Promote transparency; Achieve remarkable efficiency and speed- Reduce cost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scalability issues; - Interoperability issues; - Data accuracy issues 	[41–43]
Internet of Things (IoT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring sensors for precision; - Facilitate connection and coordination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital identification marks for food products; - Increased traceability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Significant unresolved technical issues; Lacks creativity;- Privacy concerns 	[50,51]
Artificial intelligence (AI) and Machine learning (ML)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stimulates human intelligence;- Automatic decision making 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Automatic quality control; - Improves predictability and automation; - Improves predictability and automation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data security concerns; Great complexity; Compatibility issues; Extensive energy use 	[60–63]
Virtual Reality (VR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creates a computer-generated simulation of three-dimensional environments or images 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allows users to interact with the virtual world in a realistic and tangible way 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Requires specialized equipment 	[64–67]
3D printing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Revolutionizes the creation of devices aimed at monitoring food quality, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Allows for the production of intelligent components that integrate smoothly into standard food packaging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Speed and scalability; - Material limitations; - Resolution and surface finish 	[69]

5. Challenges in implementing blockchain for food fraud

5.1. Scalability issues

Scalability is a significant obstacle when using blockchain technology, especially as the network expands. For example, a small blockchain network that tracks food items from one farm to one supermarket requires only a few nodes [70]. However, as the scale increases to include multiple farms and supermarkets, the number of nodes needed grows exponentially, potentially making the network unwieldy. This growth can lead to longer transaction times and higher costs, making it difficult to efficiently scale the system. The scalability issue becomes even more critical in large systems that handle a lot of data transactions, such as those in the food supply chain [46].

As transaction volumes increase, blockchain networks may become slower and less efficient, leading to delays and increased costs [73]. Despite the advantages in food supply chains [74], argue that there are still unresolved technical challenges with blockchain, particularly with scalability. As the number of transactions in food supply chains grows exponentially, maintaining efficiency becomes crucial [75]. The transaction validation process can also limit blockchain's effectiveness, especially in high-throughput scenarios [46], making it less suitable for scenarios such as food supply chains that require handling large amounts of data and processing many transactions quickly [75].

[97] emphasize that, comparatively, traditional transaction technologies like Visa outperform blockchain, processing thousands of transactions per second, whereas blockchain platforms like Bitcoin handle far fewer at the same time. Although there are ongoing efforts to improve blockchain scalability, such as off-chain data storage, these solutions are in the early development stages and raise additional concerns about data integrity and privacy [75]. The successful deployment of blockchain in sectors requiring high scalability and decentralization, such as food supply chains [76], depends on overcoming these challenges to ensure efficient and flexible operations.

5.2. Interoperability among different blockchain platforms

Interoperability, the ability of multiple systems to work together seamlessly, is essential in the blockchain arena, particularly for ensuring that different entities within a supply chain can effectively share and use the same data. Achieving interoperability poses significant challenges due to the diverse data formats and protocols used by various systems. This issue is especially critical in food supply chains, here there is a heightened demand for standardized protocols to enable effective integration across businesses. Despite the potential benefits, the adoption of blockchain-based solutions is hindered by the lack of universally

accepted standards and a consensus protocol [77], leading to compatibility issues between different blockchain networks [78]. This problem, known as the lack of interoperability, is a significant barrier that needs to be addressed. In the context of food supply chains, enhancing interoperability is crucial for coordinating the exchange of information across various commodities, transport modes, and information systems. The development of a Digital Food Record (DFR) is proposed as a crucial tool to facilitate whole-chain traceability, improve interoperability, connect various actors and data creators within the chain, and ultimately enhance market trust in each product delivered [79].

5.3. Data accuracy and privacy

Blockchain technology critically depends on the accuracy and completeness of the data imputed into its system; any errors or gaps can undermine the entire system's integrity. The success of blockchain-based systems, therefore, hinges significantly on the quality of data. In the context of food supply chains, the process of collecting and sharing data among various entities is crucial but also introduces significant data privacy and security concerns [12]. Sensitive information, such as trade secrets or personal data, is at risk of exposure or misused, which could damage company reputations and diminish consumer trust [80]. In the modern digital age, tools that leverage data are increasingly promoted for their potential to enhance food safety. However, realizing this potential depends on both the availability and the quality of the data. Achieving the goal of a digitally-enabled "smarter food safety" system faces several challenges, with a notable one being the hesitance among food system participants to share data. This reluctance is often driven by fears of data misuse, negative publicity, legal liabilities, and the necessity to protect confidential information, such as records of human illness. These complex issues create a tension between the utility of data and the need to safeguard privacy [81].

The rapid development of quantum computing poses significant threats to blockchain technology, particularly due to its potential to compromise cryptographic security methods through Grover's and Shor's algorithms, which threatens both public-key cryptography and hash functions. In the case of public key cryptosystems, the evolution of quantum computing attacks targets most popular public-key algorithms. These quantum algorithms endanger the integrity of public-key cryptography and hash functions, which are fundamental to blockchain security [83]. Specifically, quantum computing attacks target widely-used public-key algorithms such as the digital signature algorithm (DSA), Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA), and Rivest, Shamir, Adleman (RSA) [82]. Furthermore, Grover's algorithm enhances the capabilities of quantum computers in generating hashes at an accelerated rate. This acceleration could potentially allow for the recreation of an

entire blockchain, thereby enabling attackers to breach blockchain systems. They could achieve this by rapidly performing inverse calculations, undermining the cryptographic security that protects blockchain data, or by exploiting mining processes to compromise the integrity of public blockchains [84]. These advancements in quantum computing thus place the security of data on blockchain networks at significant risk.

Blockchain technology offers a groundbreaking approach to combating food fraud, yet it faces several challenges (Table 3), including scalability, interoperability, and issues with data accuracy and privacy, which create significant barriers to its broad adoption. Scalability concerns arise due to the growing transaction volumes within the food supply chain, necessitating innovative approaches like off-chain data storage to handle the increased data load efficiently. Interoperability is essential for seamless data exchange among various blockchain platforms. Efforts to improve this, such as the development of a Digital Food Record (DFR), are focused on enabling whole-chain traceability to ensure that all parts of the supply chain are transparent and accountable. Data accuracy and privacy are critical to the integrity of both blockchain technology and quantum computing. Accurate and private data entry is fundamental, requiring ongoing improvements in data management and privacy protection mechanisms. For example, the blockchain-cloud fusion scheme mentioned in Ref. [48] highlights efforts to refine these aspects. Addressing these challenges through collaborative efforts and technological advancements is essential for harnessing blockchain's full potential in safeguarding the global food supply chain.

5.4. Mechanisms to prevent data tampering and fraud in blockchain-based food tracing

Blockchain technology can keep a record of data in which once recorded, it cannot be changed without the consent or agreement of the participants in the system. But the problem of the data integrity of the first data entry is a distinct and challenging issue. To counter this,

Table 3
Challenges and solutions in implementing blockchain for food fraud prevention.

Challenge	Description	Solutions	Examples
Scalability	Managing an increasing number of transactions across the supply chain can be difficult as the scale of operations grows.	Develop off-chain data storage systems and enhance blockchain protocols to handle larger volumes of transactions more efficiently.	N/A
Interoperability	Different blockchain systems may have compatibility issues, making it difficult for them to work seamlessly together.	Establish universal blockchain standards and protocols that ensure different systems can communicate and operate together effectively.	The Digital Food Record (DFR) is used to achieve whole-chain traceability, exemplifying a successful application of interoperability standards.
Data accuracy and privacy	Risks include incorrect or incomplete data entry, exposure of sensitive information, and vulnerabilities to quantum computing attacks.	Refine data accuracy mechanisms and privacy protection protocols. Develop blockchain systems that are resistant to quantum computing.	The blockchain-cloud fusion scheme based on the Decentralized Autonomous Blockchain System (DABS) is cited as an example of a system enhancing data security and privacy [48].

incorporating tamper-proof IoT items into the system can be a possible solution. Such devices are capable of storing and sending data on their own and thus minimizing the chances of human's interference on the chain. For instance, the sensors that are used to measure temperature and location can link this data directly into the blockchain system making the recorded data credible [27,103]. Another way to combat food fraud using Blockchain is to introduce genetic data into the system based on the blockchain. Since the system memorizes distinct genetic markers for each given product, these may be for example DNA barcodes within the food product, the system can easily confirm the uniqueness of the product at any phase of its distribution. This way, it becomes far harder for any fraudulent actors to manipulate the product and place a fake label since the genotype data cannot be forged or substituted with another one [6]. Furthermore, blockchain systems can use cross-referencing methods in which data from various sources including IoT, data entry and genetic information are compared for consistency. The use of multi-factor verification can improve this process by way of insisting on the need to have different forms of evidence that must tally before the data is deemed genuine. For example, the verification could be based on a QR code being connected with some data from an IoT device and genetic information and if they are all a match, then the product is seen as verified [102].

In addition to these methods, smart contracts on the blockchain can be used for the automatic enforcement of rules and regulations in the supply chain. They can be designed to generate notifications or preformed actions for instance a stop on the distribution of a product in case of anomaly or inconsistency in data. This level of automation minimizes the need for manual supervision and enhances dependability of the system [104]. Also, consensus algorithms carried out in blockchain systems, where most of the users confirm the entries of data, contribute to the integrity of data. Additional ordinary checks that can be made using smart contracts or by third parties, to guarantee the validity of the data submitted and stored in the blockchain, are valuable [105].

However, as mentioned, there are other open issues that are still an object of investigation in the literature regarding fraud detection. For example, there is currently a lot of debate about the security of IoT devices against manipulation even if they are designed to be relatively tamper-resistant. Furthermore, the implementation of genetic and genomic information means utilisation of standard protocols and legal standards that are still developing. Nevertheless, the possibility of a human factor cannot be ignored in a calamity of a data entry point through either an inadvertent mistake or conscious machination. Blockchain can witness and secure data once it is captured, but the question of how to ensure that data is accurately captured to start with remains both an experimental and theoretical problem to this day [106, 107]. Despite challenges of scalability, interoperability, and doubts on the credibility of data stored, blockchain technologies are decentralized and immutable, and they provide ways through which food produce can be traced and verified and can be relied on to reduce the risk of fraud and contamination. These issues are rooted in the fact that food transactions are on an international level, various types of blockchain platforms are being applied, and input data verification is not entirely accurate [112, 113].

However, solving these problems will greatly improve the performance of the blockchain in maintaining food safety. Scalability is a challenge because the food industry operates on millions of transactions daily. Blockchain networks, particularly those using Proof of Work consensus mechanisms, often struggle to handle such large volumes of data. Most of the time, scalability and speed are inherent to the complexity of the blockchain. While solutions such as Layer 2 scaling and improved consensus algorithms, like the Proof of Stake, are being developed to tackle these issues, widespread adoption remains a challenge [108,109]. Interoperability is also an issue of concern given the diverse stakeholders that are involved in the food supply chain across the world and who may be using different block chain platforms. These platforms are not integrated because there are no standard protocols

used which ultimately results in the formation of different silos that do not have a way of communicating and sharing data with each other [110,111].

This issue remains an open problem of the current technology settlement in the blockchain because, despite its relative novelty, diverse solutions that meet the requirements of organizations have been implemented. This challenge can be addressed by ensuring that standards which foster interoperability can be provided to support these systems while at the same time making sure that the specific functionality of one system is not duplicated by another system. In addition, although the use of blockchain maintains data integrity, it does not warrant the validity of the data inputted. This indicates that mistakes can still be made or individuals can commit fraud at the stages of data entry hence reducing the credibility of the information kept in the blockchain. There is also the problem that when business data is put on a ledger anyone who has access to this ledger risks compromising its privacy. This is why these challenges exist because blockchain or its design consists of, among other things, transparency and incorruptibility that at times may be an obstacle to privacy and accuracy of the data input. The core concept of blockchain is that the data entered into it is immutable, therefore, verification should be done before the data is inputted, and it has to be accurate.

6. Overcoming obstacles: strategies and collaborative efforts

6.1. Refinement of blockchain protocols

The food market operates as a global, full-cycle system involving a vast array of players including farmers, processors, distributors, retailers, consumers [85]. Ensuring the authenticity and reliability of food along its designated path is crucial. However, current systems are often fragmented and lack the necessary transparency to effectively address supply chain issues such as food fraud, contamination, and wastage [70]. Blockchain technology offers a solution with its immutable ledger system that records every transaction or movement of goods within supply chains. This level of transparency is unparalleled as it allows every participant in the supply chain to trace food from its origin, such as the farm, to its final destination, such as the consumer's table. This traceability is not only critical for assessing food quality but also enables a swift response to any food safety incidents [71].

Blockchain's main contribution to the food market lies in its ability to clearly establish the provenance of food items and manage records of handling and storage conditions. This capability significantly reduces the potential for misconduct and ensures that safety standards are maintained throughout the supply chain. In the event of an epidemic, blockchain technology can facilitate a rapid response, helping to quickly identify and address the source of the problem, thereby preventing further spread [23]. The decentralized nature of blockchain means that no single entity controls the data, reducing the risks of data breaches or tampering. This aspect is particularly beneficial in the food industry where the privacy of sensitive data, such as trade secrets and personal information, is paramount [6].

6.2. Use of quantum-resistant blockchains

Quantum-resistant and quantum-secured blockchains are being developed to shield blockchain technologies from potential attacks by future quantum computers. These quantum-resistant signatures are crucial for secure communications and digital identity verification, as they are designed to withstand attacks from quantum computers, thereby ensuring the long-term security of digital communications and the protection of sensitive data from potential quantum attacks. An example of this technology is the use of code-based cryptosystems, which rely on the complexity of decoding certain structured linear error-correcting codes to secure signature schemes [72].

The emergence of quantum computing poses a significant threat to

the immutable nature of blockchain records and the overall security of information, which are foundational to the technology's use in supply chains. With quantum computing capabilities, an attacker could impersonate a supply chain user and take actions like accessing or altering sensitive information on the blockchain without detection. This could severely compromise the transparency and traceability of the supply chain, opening the door to opportunistic behaviours and eroding the trustworthy environment that blockchain was intended to create. Currently, there has been limited focus on how quantum-resistant blockchains could enhance data security and privacy within the food supply chain. However, it is clear that quantum-resistant cryptography will play a pivotal role in determining the future utility of blockchain in supply chain management. Addressing this emerging challenge will require collaborative efforts from various stakeholders, including governments, software developers, standard developers, blockchain experts, cryptography experts, and businesses, to expedite the development of robust quantum-resistant solutions.

6.3. Collaborative efforts among stakeholders

Cooperation and collaboration among key stakeholders are essential for ensuring food consumption safety due to the complex nature of the food sector, extensive supply chains, and the involvement of numerous organizations [86]. Each stage in the food supply chain – from harvesting raw materials to processing and retailing – must prioritize food safety. Failures at any point can lead to consumer illnesses, erode trust in the food supply, and have severe consequences. Thus, it is crucial for all involved stakeholders to work together towards this goal. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) provide a practical framework by uniting government agencies, regulators, academia, NGOs, and the private sector to collaboratively tackle the challenges affecting the safe supply and trade of food [87].

Suppliers play a critical role in preventing and detecting economic adulteration. They should adopt strategies similar to those of manufacturers and explore methods to facilitate proper testing procedures, enhance transparency, provide timely information, and collaborate with manufacturers to combat fraud [88]. Retailers must focus on partnering with reputable suppliers and manufacturers who adhere to the highest standards in deterrence and detection. Continuous monitoring of their activities is crucial. Retailers should ensure their suppliers deliver authentic and safe products free from counterfeiting [89]. Effective communication and efficient product recall processes with supply chain partners can minimize the impact of incidents, which is more crucial than ever.

To raise standards in food and product safety, consumers must demand more stringent food safety measures. Manufacturers can support these demands by helping consumers identify issues and providing resources to recognize fraudulent products, enabling them to avoid such items. Governments are responsible for establishing and enforcing consumer rights and safeguards. They can aid legitimate businesses by protecting property rights and curbing the prevalence of illegal enterprises. Moreover, customs and border protection agencies play a vital role in preventing the entry of illegal and potentially unsafe products into their countries. Tackling food fraud requires a collaborative effort between industry and government agencies, due to its complexity and global scope. It demands dedicated efforts from producers, distributors, and consumers throughout the food supply chain. Fig. 1 outlines the path from identifying the threat of food fraud to implementing innovative blockchain solutions and the collaborative efforts necessary to address these challenges. This serves as a blueprint for stakeholders seeking to understand and navigate the complexities of using blockchain technology in combating food fraud (see Fig. 2).

The application of blockchain technology highly depends on the traditional food safety and compliance framework. For the application of blockchain technology to achieve full potential, it has to be integrated with current food chain safety practices like Hazard Analysis Critical

Fig. 1. Typical flow of transaction of a blockchain technology [21].

Fig. 2. Blockchain technology strategy against food fraud [Authors' summary].

Control Points (HACCP) and ISO 22000 standards. Incorporating blockchain into such frameworks means that the stakeholders promote both transparency and immutability of the data on the blockchain as well as compliance with standard safety procedures. This integration can assist the process of automated verification of compliance and can reduce human error and increase consumer trust in the supply chain [102]. Blockchain technology can exist as an authentication and validation tool that can augment other risk management strategies. Although through the use of blockchain, it is not possible to alter the data, the input of data still needs to be subject to strict validation. They should therefore be implemented in complement with other risk management technologies like predictive analytics and real time monitoring technologies for food fraud. These technologies can then be used to alert risks at the early stages and alert deviations from standard practices

hence preventing fraud that would affect the consumers [101]. For the optimum usage of the blockchain technology, all stakeholders in the supply chain have to be informed and trained concerning the option and the advantages it brings. This comprises suppliers and manufacturers as well as regulators, customs officials, and consumers. Both of these groups must be informed on the potential of blockchain in food safety and how to interpret blockchain data. Essentially, the orientation of training programs should incorporate the need to pay independent attention to the proper inputs into a blockchain system and the need to have independent checks on a blockchain system [99,100].

Fig. 3 below showcases a flow chart the illustrates the application of blockchain technology to combat food fraud. It gives a summary of the innovations, challenges and obstacles in utilizing blockchain to prevent food fraud.

Fig. 3. Flow chart detailing an overview of blockchain technology in preventing food fraud.

7. Theoretical and practical implications

The absence of clear regulatory standards is a major barrier to adopting blockchain technology in the food section [90]. Currently, blockchain lacks specific regulations, and there is no established set of standards to guide its implementation [96]. The global nature of supply chains adds complexity, as they are subject to a myriad of laws and regulations from various national authorities, making the development of blockchain-specific legislation challenging [24]. For blockchain technology to be effectively integrated into agri-food traceability, it must be supported by legal and regulatory frameworks that ensure compliance [89].

The application of blockchain in the food industry introduces unique demands, particularly concerning how security and innovation are addressed. It necessitates a tailored regulatory environment that fills existing gaps by setting clear data governance guidelines. These standards must protect sensitive data while ensuring the transparent traceability of food items throughout the supply chain, balancing data confidentiality with supply chain transparency [90]. Economically, blockchain offers significant benefits such as enhanced traceability and cost reductions from improved operational efficiency. Historical outcomes of blockchain implementation have shown positive financial impacts, particularly for small firms. Companies that adopt blockchain to increase transparency and reliability can become leaders in their sectors [14].

Blockchain's cross-border application presents challenges, including the need to standardize and synchronize with various legal jurisdictions. International regulations should adopt a unified strategy to deliver blockchain solutions that are adaptive and reliable across different cultural environments and robustly applicable worldwide. In crisis situations, such as outbreaks of foodborne diseases or product recalls, blockchain can enhance traceability, allowing for quicker identification of issues and mitigation of risks [91].

Furthermore, blockchain positively impacts sustainable food practices by improving the traceability of eco-friendly sourcing methods. This enhances traceability can help reduce food waste and streamline the food supply chain, supporting the industry's drive towards

sustainability [92]. However, notable challenges to blockchain adoption in the food sector include technological complexity, stakeholder resistance, and the need for significant upfront investments. Overcoming these obstacles requires providing education, opportunities for stakeholders to engage with the technology, and supportive measures to facilitate the transition [93].

In research, there are many possibilities for the investigation of the measures for forming the standardized norms that regulate blockchain in the sphere of its international application. Future research could analyze the wider socio-economic effects of blockchain for the small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) within the food industry, especially where and how these companies could use the technology to improve their place in the value chain. Another research direction which can be deemed appropriate is the analyses of the consumers' perceptions of the transparency enabled by blockchain solutions and its impact on the purchasing behavior; although such investigation would assist in enlarging the understanding of the potential of blockchain in terms of reshaping the consumers' trust.

From a utilitarian perspective, the application of the blockchain revolutionizes almost every aspect of the food industry. For example, Walmart has implemented the use of blockchain to track leafy greens from farms to Walmart stores, by using blockchain the time required to trace a source of food poisoning can be decreased to a minimum which in a way improves the quality of food safety [31]. In the same way, through employing blockchain technology to the procurement, processing, packaging, storage, and distribution of chicken products, Carrefour guarantees the consumers full information concerning the product's journey, right from the farm, farming practices, and the quality assurance processes [98]. These examples show how blockchain can increase productivity and build an organisation's credibility by offering consumers more clarity and confidence.

The application of blockchain in the food industry is beneficial in the supply chain, on a societal perspective as it will help encourage sustainable practices in food production and distribution. By applying traceability, blockchain can decrease food fraud and waste thereby enhancing increase in responsible consumption patterns Furthermore, the technology responds to the need of emerging sustainable supply

chains and enabling the verification of environmentally friendly sources and production methods. This societal impact resonates with the increasing consumer concern over the production of foods, and more specifically, the processes that create them thereby resulting in a more sustainable and trustworthy food system.

8. Conclusion and future directions

Blockchain technology has the capability of improving the safety and quality of the food supply chain around the world by offering credibility of origin and responsible authorities. However, issues like scalability, compatibility, accuracy, and security are still critical issues that need to be addressed before it can deliver its full potential. This calls for the advancement of solutions through innovations and cross stakeholder engagements to adopt advanced technologies such as the IoT and Artificial Intelligence and implement the required change in the food supply chain so as to enhance a secure food supply chain and customers' health. The key findings presented in this research emphasize the benefits of blockchain in providing traceability and accountability which can become a lever for improving the quality and safety of the food supply chain. However, the success of blockchain is regarded on the accuracy of the data fed into the system. Wrong or insufficient data can also compromise on the credibility of the system as a whole, and therefore means to improve data credibility and system efficiency have to be sought by coming up with more creative ideas.

More research should be directed towards the interaction between blockchain and other advanced technologies such as AI and IoT that can improve real-time visibility analysis, as well as other performance indicators of the decentralized supply chain. Researchers should also focus on decentralized data adjustment processes that will further help decentralization of blockchain and make the networks more resistant to tampering thereby enhancing the market transparency of the markets. Moreover, added future opportunities to use smart contracts can be applied to optimize compliance and quality assurance thereby reducing the role of human error and improve the effectiveness of anti-fraud. For an industry practitioner, there is a need to take certain specific measures in order to enhance the possibility of the implementation of blockchain technology. This involves designing of architectures that are decentralized, the integration of genomic data for accurate food authentication, and Smart Contracts to enhance decentralized supply chains. In this way, consumers and all industry related parties will be guaranteed that every food product is traceable, safe, and of high quality in order to increase consumers' confidence in the use of food products, increase food safety, and sustain the food industry.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Keru Duan: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.
Helen Onyeaka: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.
Gu Pang: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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